

Polarographic and cyclic voltammetric studies on 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-[4'-sulphonamoyl]azopyrimidines

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Electrochemical behaviour of 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-[4'-sulphonamoyl]azopyrimidines has been studied at DME and GC electrodes by employing techniques such as d.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry and coulometry in Britton-Robinson buffers (pH 2.8–11.5). The reduction gives one well-defined, irreversible and diffusion-controlled, 2-electron wave/peak corresponding to the reduction of $-N=N-$ to $-NH-NH-$. The product obtained by constant current electrolysis has been analysed and plausible mechanism for the reduction process is suggested. Effect of solvent composition has also been studied.

Electrochemical investigations provide valuable information about the redox behaviour of biological active compounds which ultimately lead to a better understanding of the behaviour of these compounds in living systems^{1,2}. Literature survey reveals that in spite of the presence of three biological active sites, i.e. sulphonamoyl³, azo⁴ and pyrimidine⁵ nucleus in the molecular framework, the compound 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-[4'-sulphonamoyl]azopyrimidine (A) and its derivatives have not been studied electrochemically. In this communication redox behaviour of these compounds at dropping mercury and glassy carbon electrode has been reported.

Results and Discussion

In the pH range 2.8–11.5 all sulphonamoylazopyrimidines exhibit single, 2e wave/peak (Fig. 1). The electrochemical characteristics are summarised in Table 1. The wave/peak is attributed to the reduction of azo group on the basis of other reported azo compounds⁶. The electrode process was found to be diffusion-controlled⁷ on the basis of linear plots of i_d vs $v^{1/2}$, and i_d/i_p vs concentration of depolarizer plots which pass through the origin. This is also evident by the low value of temperature coefficient (below 1.62%/deg.). The irreversible nature of the wave/peak was established from the shift of $E_{1/2}/E_p$ towards negative potential with increase in concentration of depolarizer and $\log i_p$ plot analysis⁸. Absence of anodic

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-(4'-methyl-oxazolylsulphonamoyl)azopyrimidine at pH 4.7, conc = 2×10^{-4} M at scan rate; (1) 100, (2) 150, (3) 200 mV s^{-1} .

peak also lends support to the irreversible nature of the waves and peaks. The two segments in $E_{1/2}/E_p$ vs pH plots with break at pH 7.7 clearly show the participation of proton in the reduction process⁹. Above pH 7.7, the $E_{1/2}/E_p$ becomes independent of pH. This indicates the reduction of unprotonated species. Similar dependence of half-wave potential on pH has also been reported by other workers in the case of azo compounds.

The value of αn_a (product of transfer coefficient and number of electrons involved per molecule of the reactant) and P (number of protons involved per molecule of the reactant in the rate determining step) were calculated using following equations⁸.

$$E_{3/4} - E_{1/4} = 0.0517/\alpha n_a$$

$$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH} = \frac{0.05917}{\alpha n_a} \cdot P$$

The value of P was found to be one. Controlled potential electrolysis of the compound at the plateau potential (1.2 V) using the mercury pool cathode consumed 2.0 electrons. The gradual decrease and final disappearance of the colour of catholyte solution was observed. The

polarogram and cyclic voltammogram of the completely reduced solution did not show any reduction wave/peak. This clearly indicates that no electroactive species remained in the solution after complete electroreduction of the compound.

Table 1. Electrochemical characteristics of 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-[4'-sulphonamoyl]azopyrimidines

pH = 3.6, Conc. = $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$						
Compd. no.	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μA	$-E_p$ V	$\frac{dE_{1/2}}{dpH}$ V/pH	$I \times 10^{-3}$	αn_a
1	0.80	1.60	0.78	0.06	29.3	0.72
2	1.02	3.20	1.09	0.05	58.6	0.84
3	1.20	2.70	1.18	0.08	49.5	0.51
4	0.72	2.30	0.71	0.04	42.1	0.64

Since exocyclic $-N=N-$ is more susceptible¹⁰ to reduction in comparison to nuclear site of 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-[4'-sulphonamoyl]azopyrimidine, it was concluded that polarographic wave is due to the reduction of azo group. Studies of other workers^{11,12} and findings of controlled potential electrolysis suggest that $-N=N-$ is reduced to $-NH-NH-$ consuming two electrons. Reduction upto $-NH-NH-$ stage is also supported by the negative amino group test given by catholyte obtained after controlled potential electrolysis.

On the basis of the above findings, the mechanism proposed for the reduction process at d.m.e. and g.c. electrodes, is presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Effect of solvent composition: In order to determine the effect of solvent composition, the amount of dimethylformamide in test solution was gradually increased from 30 to 70%. It was found that with an increase in the percentage of dimethylformamide diffusion current decreases (Table 2). This decrease in diffusion current was observed due to the decrease in the concentration of the electroactive species, i.e. protonated 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-[4'-sulphonamoyl]azopyrimidine.

The values of $E_{1/2}$ also shifted towards more negative potential with increase in the percentage of dimethylformamide (Table 2). An increase in the organic solvent content resulted a rise in pH¹³ and increase in the dissociation constant of the protonated species. The rise in pH decreases the availability of H^+ for the formation of electroactive species and the increase in the dissociation constant decreases the stability of the electroactive protonated species¹⁴. Both these factors lower the rate of protonation and consequently would lead to a shift in half-wave potential of the wave towards more negative potential in all such cases where protonation precedes the electron transfer. It appears that these two factors only are not responsible for the observed shift in the $E_{1/2}$ because the resulted shift is greater than that it would have been due to change in pH and the dissociation constant. An increase in percentage of dimethylformamide from 30 to 60% resulted in an increase of pH by 1.20 unit.

Table 2. Effect of solvent composition on the polarographic reduction of 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-[4'-guanylsulphonamoyl]azopyrimidines

pH = 3.6, Conc. = $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$			
Compd. no.	DMF %	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μA
1	30	0.80	1.60
2	40	0.82	1.53
3	50	0.86	1.45
4	60	0.90	1.37
5	70	0.92	1.22

This additional shift in $E_{1/2}$ may be ascribed to a decrease in absorbability and hence, surface concentration of the depolarizer with an increasing percentage of DMF in aqueous organic mixture¹⁵. Obviously, decreased surface concentration would retard the electrode process¹⁶ resulting in decrease in i_d and shift in $E_{1/2}$ towards negative potential.

Experimental

2-Amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-[4'-sulphonamoyl]azopyrimidine were synthesised¹⁷ and the purity was ascertained by m.p. and tlc. Stock solutions ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) of azopyrimidines were prepared in dimethylformamide. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Equipment used and experimental details are reported elsewhere¹⁸.

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